

Classification of pesticides and its damaging effects: a review.

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ABSTRACT

Organophosphate (OP) pesticides, as a group, are most widely used insecticides in India. OP pesticides are generally used on fruits, vegetables, grains, and pasture seed, cotton, on livestock and domestic animals as well as for building pest control. Pesticides compounds represent an important class of pollutants for food, soil and surface water resources. These pesticides remain in the fruits and vegetables and cannot be removed even after washing which is very harmful and affects the human health, so to remove or neutralize these harmful pesticides some alternative action has to be taken or be implemented. Four pesticides mainly organophosphate pesticides namely chlorpyrifos, dimethoate, Malathion and monocrotophos are the most widely used pesticides used in vegetables and fruits especially brinjals and grapes. This paper helps in reviewing the impact of pesticides, its extent of danger, its effect in day to day life, measures taken to use pesticides and the precautions one should undertake while dealing with harmful pesticides.

KEYWORDS: Pesticides, chlorpyrifos, Malathion, Dimethoate, toxicity, carcinogen.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pesticides are chemical substances used to kill insects and animals that destroy crops. They are characterized by pronounced persistence against chemical/biological degradation, high environmental mobility, strong tendency for bioaccumulation in human and animal tissues, and significant impacts on human health and the environment, even at extremely low concentrations.

India is a predominantly agrarian country with about 60-80% rural population. Pesticides are routinely used for advanced farming (Anuj Thapar et al., 2015). These are readily available over the counter. Therefore, a pesticide is an easy access source for suicidal purpose particularly after trivial family squabbles. Such little petty quarrels often that result in consumption of pesticide for suicide purpose is a matter of routine news in local dailies. Poisoning is seldom included as a priority for health research in India, though every year, hundreds of people are

losing their lives prematurely from pesticide poisoning (HS Bawasker et al., 2005). Pesticides are a class of chemical substances used against organisms damaging humans, animals, and plants, such as insects, fungi, moulds, nematode, and rodents. These compounds represent an important class of pollutants for food, ground and surface water resources (M C Bruzzoniti et al., 2006). The majority of such substances are applied directly to the soil or sprayed over crop fields and hence released directly to the environment. The organophosphorus insecticides (OPPs) have an important role in the agricultural pest control. However, the continued use of organophosphorus insecticides increases the possibility of residues of these compounds being found in some vegetables, fruits threatening the alimentary security.

2. CLASSIFICATION OF PESTICIDES

Pesticides can be classified by target organism (e.g., herbicides, insecticides, fungicides, target organism (e.g., organic, inorganic, synthetic, or biological (biopesticide), although the distinction can sometimes blur), and physical state (e.g. gaseous (fumigant)). Bio pesticides include microbial pesticides and biochemical pesticides. Herbicides, also commonly known as weed killers,

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are pesticides used to kill unwanted plants. Selective herbicides kill specific targets, while leaving the desired crop relatively unharmed. Some of these act by interfering with the growth of the weed and are often synthetic mimics of natural plant hormones. Herbicides used to clear waste ground, industrial sites, railways and railway embankments are not selective and kill all plant material with which they come into contact. Smaller quantities are used in forestry, pasture systems, and management of areas set aside as wildlife habitat. Fungicides are biocidal chemical compounds or biological organisms used to kill or inhibit fungi or fungal spores. Fungi can cause serious damage in agriculture, resulting in critical losses of yield, quality, and profit. Fungicides are used both in agriculture and to fight fungal infections in animals. Chemicals used to control oomycetes, which are not fungi, are also referred to as fungicides as oomycetes use the same mechanisms as fungi to infect plants. Fungicides can either be contact, Trans laminar or systemic. Contact fungicides are not taken up into the plant tissue, and protect only the plant where the spray is deposited; Trans laminar fungicides redistribute the fungicide from the upper, sprayed leaf surface to the lower, unsprayed surface; systemic fungicides are taken up and redistributed through the xylem vessels. Few fungicides move to all parts of a plant. Some are locally systemic, and some move upwardly.

An insecticide is a substance used to kill insects. They include ovicides and larvicides used against insect eggs and larvae, respectively. Insecticides are used in agriculture, medicine, industry and by consumers. Insecticides are claimed to be a major factor behind the increase in agricultural 20th century's productivity. Nearly all insecticides have the potential to significantly alter ecosystems; many are toxic to humans; some concentrate along the food chain. Insecticides can be classified in two major groups as systemic insecticide which have residual or long term activity and contact insecticides, which have no residual activity. Acaricides are pesticides that kill members of the arachnid subclass Acari, which includes ticks and mites. Acaricides are used both in medicine and agriculture, although the desired selective toxicity differs between the two fields. A bactericide or bacteriocide, sometimes abbreviated Bcidal, is a substance that kills bacteria. Bactericides are disinfectants, antiseptics, or antibiotics. A biocide is a chemical substance or microorganism which can deter, render harmless, or exert a controlling effect on any harmful organism by chemical or biological means. Biocides are commonly used in medicine, agriculture, forestry, and industry. Biocidal substances and products are also employed as anti-fouling agents or disinfectants under other circumstances: chlorine, for example, is used as a short-life biocide in industrial water

treatment but as a disinfectant in swimming pools (H. Liu et al., 2009). Many biocides are synthetic, but a class of natural biocides, derived from, e.g., bacteria and plants. A bio-herbicide is a biologically based control agent for weeds. Among the three major types of pesticides (agricultural pest-control agents) herbicides are used to control weeds, or undesirable plants. Biopesticides, a contraction of 'biological pesticides', include several types of pest management intervention: through predatory, parasitic, or chemical relationships. The term has been associated historically with biological control - and by implication - the manipulation of living organisms. Regulatory positions can be influenced by public perceptions, thus:

- In the EU, Biopesticides have been defined as "a form of pesticide based on micro-organisms or natural products".
- The US EPA states that they "include naturally occurring substances that control pests (biochemical pesticides), microorganisms that control pests (microbial pesticides), and pesticidal substances produced by plants containing added genetic material (plant-incorporated protectants) or PIPs".

Molluscicides, also known as snail baits and snail pellets, are pesticides against molluscs, which are usually used in agriculture or gardening, in order to control gastropod pests specifically slugs and snails which damage crops or other valued plants by feeding on them.

A nematicide is a type of chemical pesticide used to kill plant-parasitic nematodes. Nematicides have tended to be broad-spectrum toxicants possessing high volatility or other properties promoting migration through the soil. Temik (Aldicarb), a carbamate insecticide marketed by Bayer Crop Science, is an example of a commonly used commercial nematicide. It is important in potato production, where it has been used for control of soil-borne nematodes

A piscicide is a chemical substance which is poisonous to fish. The primary use for piscicides is to eliminate a dominant species of fish in a body of water, as the first step in attempting to populate the body of water with a different fish. They are also used to combat parasitic and invasive species of fish. Rodenticides, colloquially rat poison, are typically non-specific pest control chemicals made and sold for the purpose of killing rodents. Some rodenticides are lethal after one exposure while others require more than one. Rodents are disinclined to gorge on an unknown food (perhaps reflecting an adaptation to their inability to vomit), preferring to sample, wait and observe whether it makes them or other rats sick. This phenomenon of bait shyness or poison shyness is the rationale for poisons that kill only after multiple doses. General population is mainly exposed to organophosphorus pesticide residues through the ingestion of contaminated foods (such as cereals,

vegetables, and fruits), which are directly treated with OPPs pesticides or are grown in contaminated fields. Compared with organochlorine pesticides, OPPs demonstrate relatively low environmental persistence but a higher toxicity acute. Pesticide production and use in the country shows a different pattern from global trends – insecticide use is around 75% in the country, compared to 32% in the world. Herbicide use is only 12% in the country while worldwide, consumption is 47%. Important to note is the fact that weeding is a critical agricultural operation that provides employment to millions of poor agricultural labour, especially women, in the country. Similarly, while carbamate and synthetic pyrethroid compounds are used the most globally [45% together], in India, organophosphates constitute 50% of the consumption. Similarly, bio-pesticides are used only up to 1% amongst all pesticides in India, while worldwide, it is 12% (M C Bruzzone et al., 2006). OPs are a particular public health concern in developing countries, because they cause the majority of acute pesticide poisonings. Besides the fact that such poisonings can be life-threatening, severe poisonings caused by particular OPs have been associated with a persistent neurological impairment that may ensue a few weeks after the recovery from acute poisoning, so-called Organophosphate-induced Delayed Polyneuropathy (OPIDP). Acute poisoning by Ops may result in nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, abdominal cramps, weakness, headache, poor concentration, salivation, and sweating. In serious cases, respiratory failure and death can occur.

Chlorpyrifos:

Chlorpyrifos is an organophosphate insecticide. Pure chlorpyrifos is made up of white or colorless crystals. It has a slightly skunky odor, like rotten eggs or garlic. Chlorpyrifos is used to control many different kinds of pests, including termites, mosquitoes, and roundworms. Chlorpyrifos was first registered as an insecticide in 1965 and the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) re-registered it in 2006. The only legal indoor use for chlorpyrifos is in containers with treated baits. Products with chlorpyrifos in them are used in agriculture for feed and food crops and in cattle ear tags. They may be used on golf courses, and to control fire ants and mosquitoes for public health purposes. Products containing chlorpyrifos are also used to treat wood fences and utility poles.

Effects of chlorpyrifos and its Exposure:

Chlorpyrifos can be harmful if it is touched, inhaled, or eaten. Chlorpyrifos works by blocking an enzyme which controls messages that travel between nerve cells. When the enzyme is blocked, the nervous system can't send normal signals. This causes the nervous system to malfunction and this is how it eventually kills the pest. People can be

exposed to pesticides by eating them, breathing them in, or getting them on the skin or in the eyes. You could be exposed to chlorpyrifos if you apply products containing chlorpyrifos either as part of your job or outside of your own home. If a bait station in the house contains chlorpyrifos, people or pets could be exposed if the bait station is broken. People could be exposed to chlorpyrifos if their well water has been contaminated. This can happen if products containing chlorpyrifos were used near the well for termite control. Risks can be reduced by always reading the entire label and following all instructions (James Roberts et al., 2013). Chlorpyrifos affects the nervous system of people, pets, and other animals the same way it affects the target pest. Signs and symptoms can appear within minutes to hours after exposure. These effects can last for days or even weeks. During this time, the body is replacing the depleted enzymes in the nervous system so it can function normally again. Exposure to small amounts of chlorpyrifos can cause runny nose, tears, and increased saliva or drooling. People may sweat, and develop headache, nausea, and dizziness. More serious exposures can cause vomiting, abdominal muscle cramps, muscle twitching, tremors and weakness, and loss of coordination. Sometimes people develop diarrhea or blurred or darkened vision. In severe poisoning cases, exposure can lead to unconsciousness, loss of bladder and bowel control, convulsions, difficulty in breathing, and paralysis (Smegal, 2015).

Action of chlorpyrifos when it enters the body:

Chlorpyrifos moves to all parts of the body after exposure. Chlorpyrifos itself is not toxic, but when the body tries to break it down, it creates a toxic form. This toxic form, called chlorpyrifos Oxon, binds permanently to enzymes which control the messages that travel between nerve cells. When chlorpyrifos binds to too many of the enzymes, nerves and muscles do not function correctly. The body then must make more enzymes so that normal nerve function can resume. The body can break down and excrete most of the unbound chlorpyrifos in feces and urine within a few days. Chlorpyrifos that finds its way into the nervous system may stay there much longer.

Chlorpyrifos more sensitive to children than adults:

Chlorpyrifos exposure was linked to changes in social behavior and brain development as well as developmental delays in young laboratory animals. Other studies showed that chlorpyrifos affected the nervous system of young mice, rats, and rabbits more severely than adult animals. Researchers studied the blood of women who were exposed to chlorpyrifos and the blood of their children from birth for three years. Children who had chlorpyrifos in their

blood had more developmental delays and disorders than children who did not have chlorpyrifos in their blood. Exposed children also had more attention deficit disorders and hyperactivity disorders. In general, children may be more sensitive to pesticides than adults. One reason for this is that their bodies may break down pesticides differently. Children are also more likely to be exposed to pesticides when playing and may put their hands in their mouths more often than adults. Children may also be more sensitive to exposures because they have more surface area of skin for their body size than adults.

Effect of chlorpyrifos on the environment:

When chlorpyrifos gets into the soil, it can take weeks to years for all of the chlorpyrifos to break down. Chlorpyrifos in the soil may be broken down by ultraviolet light and chemicals in the soil. Soil temperature and pH level may also affect how long chlorpyrifos stays in the soil. Chlorpyrifos will break down more slowly in acidic soils than in basic soils. Once chlorpyrifos is in the soil, it sticks very strongly to soil particles. Plant roots won't usually pick it up, and it won't easily get into groundwater. Chlorpyrifos may wash into rivers or streams if erosion moves the treated soil. One of the breakdown products of chlorpyrifos, called TCP, does not bind to soil and may get into groundwater. Most of the chlorpyrifos applied to plant leaves will evaporate, but some may remain for 10 to 14 days. Chlorpyrifos or the chemicals it breaks into may get into the atmosphere and travel long distances. Researchers found chlorpyrifos in indoor air, dust, carpets, and on children's toys in homes where products with chlorpyrifos in them had been used.

Effect of chlorpyrifos on birds, fish, or other wildlife:

Chlorpyrifos is toxic to many bird species such as grackles and pigeons, and it is moderately toxic to others such as mallard ducks. Mallard ducks fed chlorpyrifos laid fewer eggs and raised fewer ducklings. The eggshells were thinner than normal, and many of the young ducklings died. Of all birds, robins are most often found dead following accidents involving chlorpyrifos use. Chlorpyrifos is also very toxic to fish and aquatic invertebrates. It may build up in the tissues of fish and other animals that eat smaller animals. This is known as bioaccumulation. Chlorpyrifos is very toxic to bees. It can poison non-target insects for up to 24 hours after it is sprayed. Chlorpyrifos can be toxic to earthworms for up to 2 weeks after it is applied to soil (Chritensen K et al., 2009).

Chlorpyrifos toxicological effects:

Acute toxicity:

Chlorpyrifos is moderately toxic to humans. Poisoning from chlorpyrifos may affect the central

nervous system, the cardiovascular system, and the respiratory system. It is also a skin and eye irritant (M A Gallo et al., 1991). While some organophosphates are readily absorbed through the skin, studies in humans suggest that skin absorption of chlorpyrifos is limited (N J Lawryk et al., 1991). Symptoms of acute exposure to organophosphate or cholinesterase-inhibiting compounds may include the following: numbness, tingling sensations, incoordination, headache, dizziness, tremor, nausea, abdominal cramps, sweating, blurred vision, difficulty breathing or respiratory depression, and slow heartbeat. Very high doses may result in unconsciousness, incontinence, and convulsions or fatality. Persons with respiratory ailments, recent exposure to cholinesterase inhibitors, cholinesterase impairment, or liver malfunction are at increased risk from exposure to chlorpyrifos. Some organophosphates may cause delayed symptoms beginning 1 to 4 weeks after an acute exposure which may or may not have produced immediate symptoms (N J Lawryk et al., 1991). In such cases, numbness, tingling, weakness, and cramping may appear in the lower limbs and progress to incoordination and paralysis. Improvement may occur over months or years, and in some cases residual impairment will remain (N J Lawryk et al., 1991). Plasma cholinesterase levels activity have been shown to be inhibited when chlorpyrifos particles are inhaled (Hazardous Substance Data Bank, 1995). The oral LD50 for chlorpyrifos in rats is 95 to 270 mg/kg. The LD50 for chlorpyrifos is 60 mg/kg in mice, 1000 mg/kg in rabbits, 32 mg/kg in chickens, 500 to 504 mg/kg in guinea pigs, and 800 mg/kg in sheep. The dermal LD50 is greater than 2000 mg/kg in rats, and 1000 to 2000 mg/kg in rabbits. The 4-hour inhalation LC50 for chlorpyrifos in rats is greater than 0.2 mg/L (Elanco, 1992).

Chronic toxicity:

Repeated or prolonged exposure to organophosphates may result in the same effects as acute exposure including the delayed symptoms. Other effects reported in workers repeatedly exposed include impaired memory and concentration, disorientation, severe depressions, irritability, confusion, headache, speech difficulties, delayed reaction times, nightmares, sleepwalking, and drowsiness or insomnia. An influenza-like condition with headache, nausea, weakness, loss of appetite, and malaise has also been reported (Hazardous Substance Data Bank, 1995). When technical chlorpyrifos was fed to dogs for 2 years, increased liver weight occurred at 3.0 mg/kg/day. Signs of cholinesterase inhibition occurred at 1 mg/kg/day. Rats and mice given technical chlorpyrifos in the diet for 104 weeks showed no adverse effects other than cholinesterase inhibition. Two-year feeding studies using doses of 1 and 3 mg/kg/day of chlorpyrifos in rats showed moderate depression of cholinesterase.

Cholinesterase levels recovered when the experimental feeding was discontinued (N J Lawryk et al., 1991). Identical results occurred in a 2-year feeding study with dogs. No long term health effects were seen in either the dog or rat study. A measurable change in plasma and red blood cell cholinesterase levels was seen in workers exposed to chlorpyrifos spray. Human volunteers who ingested 0.1 mg/kg/day of chlorpyrifos for 4 weeks showed significant plasma cholinesterase inhibition.

Reproductive effects:

Current evidence indicates that chlorpyrifos does not adversely affect reproduction. In two studies, no effects were seen in animals tested at dose levels up to 1.2 mg/kg/day. No effects on reproduction occurred in a three-generation study with rats fed dietary doses as high as 1 mg/kg/day. In another study in which rats were fed 1.0 mg/kg/day for two generations, the only effect observed was a slight increase in the number of deaths of newborn offspring (N J Lawryk et al., 1991).

Teratogenic effects:

Available evidence suggests that chlorpyrifos is not teratogenic. No teratogenic effects in offspring were found when pregnant rats were fed doses as high as 15 mg/kg/day for 10 days. When pregnant mice were given doses of 25 mg/kg/day for 10 days, minor skeletal variations and a decrease in fetal length occurred. No birth defects were seen in the offspring of male and female rats fed 1.0 mg/kg/day during a three-generation reproduction and fertility study (Documentation of the Threshold Limit Values and Biological Exposure Indices., 1986).

Mutagenic effects:

There is no evidence that chlorpyrifos is mutagenic. No evidence of mutagenicity was found in any of four tests performed (Registration Standard for the Reregistration of Pesticide Products Containing Chlorpyrifos, 2014).

Carcinogenic effects:

There is no evidence that chlorpyrifos is carcinogenic. There was no increase in the incidence of tumors when rats were fed 10 mg/kg/day for 104 weeks, nor when mice were fed 2.25 mg/kg/day for 105 weeks (Registration Standard for the Reregistration of Pesticide Products Containing Chlorpyrifos, 2014).

Malathion:

Malathion is an insecticide in the chemical family known as organophosphates. Products containing Malathion are used outdoors to control a wide variety of insects in agricultural settings and around people's homes. Malathion has also been used in public health mosquito control and fruit fly eradication programs. Malathion may also be found in some

special shampoos for treating lice. Malathion was first registered for use in the United States in 1956.

Effects of Malathion:

Malathion kills insects by preventing their nervous system from working properly. When healthy nerves send signals to each other, a special chemical messenger travels from one nerve to another to continue the message. The nerve signal stops when an enzyme is released into the space between the nerves. Malathion binds to the enzyme and prevents the nerve signal from stopping. This causes the nerves to signal each other without stopping. The constant nerve signals make it so the insects can't move or breathe normally and they die.

People, pets and other animals can be affected the same way as insects if they are exposed to enough Malathion. About the same amount of Malathion will be taken into the body whether you breathe it in or you swallow it. Malathion is also readily taken into the body through skin, though the amount absorbed will depend on where the exposure occurs on the body. Malathion can become more toxic if it has been sitting for a long time, especially in a hot place (C D Tomlin et al., 2006).

In both humans and animals, Malathion travels to the liver and kidneys and affects the nervous system. Generally, the body can break down Malathion and remove it quickly. Studies in rats showed that most Malathion was gone from their bodies within a day of exposure

Exposure to Malathion:

You could be exposed to Malathion if you get it on your skin or breathe it in, or if you use a product and eat, drink, or smoke afterwards without washing your hands. People who apply products containing Malathion may be exposed if they do not wear the proper protective equipment. You could also be exposed to residues of Malathion if you ate food that had been treated with this pesticide

Signs and symptoms when exposed to Malathion:

People who were exposed to enough Malathion to become sick felt nauseated or vomited had muscle tremors, cramps, weakness, shortness of breath, a slowed heart rate, headache, abnormal pain and diarrhea. Pets could be exposed to Malathion if they get into a product by accident, or touch or eat plants that have just been sprayed. Pets will be affected by Malathion like other animals. The nervous system is very similar in people and other animals, so animals poisoned by Malathion may show signs similar to those observed in people.

Children more sensitive to Malathion than adults:

While children may be especially sensitive to pesticides compared to adults, there are currently no

data showing that children have increased sensitivity specifically to Malathion.

Effect of Malathion on the environment

Bacteria in the soil may break down Malathion and sunlight can break down Malathion in the air. Malathion will mix with water and can move quickly through soil. Because of these properties, Malathion can be found in surface waters such as streams, and sometimes it is found in well water. The time it takes for Malathion to break down to half of the original amount in soil is about 17 days, depending on the soil type. This length of time is known as the half-life. In water, Malathion has a half-life between 2 and 18 days, depending on conditions like temperature and pH. Malathion vapor may also move long distances in air or fog (D J Blodgett et al., 2006).

Malathion is highly toxic to bees and other beneficial insects, some fish, and other aquatic life. Malathion is moderately toxic to other fish and birds, and is considered low in toxicity to mammals (J A Gervais et al., 2009).

Malathion toxicological effects:

Acute:

In acute oral doses symptoms are similar to other cholinesterase (ChE) inhibitors and include: numbness, decreased coordination, dizziness, tremor, nausea, blurred vision, difficulty breathing, slow heartbeat, headache and tingling sensation. Accidental death in humans from Malathion has been documented. Toxicity may vary based on gender, as male and female rats displayed different LD50 values for an oral dose (5400 and 5700 mg/kg, respectively).

Chronic:

In a chronic toxicity study, human volunteers ingested a low dose for 1.5 months without detrimental effects to blood ChE activity.

Carcinogenicity:

According to the EPA, Malathion has, "suggestive evidence of carcinogenicity" (Toxicological Profile for Malathion, 2003).

Dimethoate:

One of the most widely-used insecticides in the world, dimethoate is a particular concern to those exposed occupationally during manufacture, formulation and use. It is acutely toxic, has possible links to cancer and is suspected of causing birth defects.

Dimethoate is a widely used organophosphorus (OP) insecticide applied to kill mites and insects systemically and on contact. It was introduced in the 1950s, originally patented by American Cyanamid, and is now produced by 39 companies around the world. Dimethoate is used against a broad range of insects such as thrips, aphids, mites, and whiteflies,

and on a number of crops including citrus, cotton, fruit, olives, potatoes, tea, tobacco and vegetables. It is also permitted for the control of the flies in livestock accommodation, home gardens and food storage. Like all OPs, dimethoate acts by interfering with the activities of cholinesterase, an enzyme essential for the proper functioning of the nervous system of insects and humans.

Effects on wildlife and environment:

The toxicity of dimethoate for aquatic organisms and birds is moderate to high. One study found that it causes temporary rhythm alterations in some bird seed-eating species. Whilst these effects may not be fatal, they may be critical for the birds' food-finding ability and in making them more vulnerable to predators. Dimethoate has also been found to affect wood mice behavior and to cause jumping, erratic movement imbalance and death in fish. Dimethoate is highly toxic to bees on an acute contact basis, particular concern has been expressed over this. The LD50 (oral and topical) for bees is 0.1-0.2 µg/bee. Products containing dimethoate warn not to apply to crops in open flower nor when flowering weeds are present. Dimethoate is a mobile, yet relatively non-persistent OP insecticide. The primary route of dissipation appears to be microbial-mediated degradation in anaerobic (oxygen-rich) soil, particularly under moist conditions, with a half-life (time taken to degrade to half its initial strength) of 2.4 days. The 1999 ACP review discussed its previous concerns over environmental fate and behavior. They concluded that dimethoate was unlikely to leach because it is so rapidly degraded in soil, is non-volatile, was slightly persistent in sediment/water systems with a DT50 of 13-17 days and did not significantly partition to sediment.

Dimethoate toxicological effects:

Acute toxicity:

Dimethoate is moderately toxic by ingestion, inhalation and dermal absorption. As with all organophosphates, dimethoate is readily absorbed through the skin. Skin which has come in contact with this material should be washed immediately with soap and water and all contaminated clothing should be removed. Organophosphates are easily absorbed through the lungs. Persons with respiratory ailments, recent exposure to cholinesterase inhibitors, impaired cholinesterase production, or with liver malfunction may be at increased risk from exposure to dimethoate. High environmental temperatures or exposure of dimethoate to visible or UV light may enhance its toxicity (MSDS for Dimethoate, 1991). Dimethoate is not irritating to the eyes of lab animals. Severe eye irritation has occurred in workers manufacturing dimethoate. Another chemical in the formula is thought to be the cause. Firefighters exposed to fumes of burning dimethoate have

developed eye irritations (A Medicinia et al., 1982). Splashing of dimethoate into the eye may cause very swollen eyelids and damage to the cornea (the outer surface of the eye). Both of these symptoms should rapidly clear up. The organophosphate insecticides are cholinesterase inhibitors. They are highly toxic by all routes of exposure. When inhaled, the first effects are usually respiratory and may include bloody or runny nose, coughing, chest discomfort, difficult or short breath, and wheezing due to constriction or excess fluid in the bronchial tubes. Skin contact with organophosphates may cause localized sweating and involuntary muscle contractions. Eye contact will cause pain, bleeding, tears, pupil constriction, and blurred vision. Following exposure by any route, other systemic effects may begin within a few minutes or be delayed for up to 12 hours. These may include pallor, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, abdominal cramps, headache, dizziness, eye pain, blurred vision, constriction or dilation of the eye pupils, tears, salivation, sweating, and confusion. Severe poisoning will affect the central nervous system, producing incoordination, slurred speech, loss of reflexes, weakness, fatigue, involuntary muscle contractions, twitching, tremors of the tongue or eyelids, and eventually paralysis of the body extremities and the respiratory muscles. In severe cases there may also be involuntary defecation or urination, psychosis, irregular heartbeats, unconsciousness, convulsions and coma. Death may be caused by respiratory failure or cardiac arrest (MSDS for Dimethoate, 1991).

Some organophosphates may cause delayed symptoms beginning 1 to 4 weeks after an acute exposure which may or may not have produced immediate symptoms. In such cases, numbness, tingling, weakness and cramping may appear in the lower limbs and progress to incoordination and paralysis. Improvement may occur over months or years, but some residual impairment will remain (MSDS for Dimethoate, 1991). The amount of a chemical that is lethal to one-half (50%) of experimental animals fed the material is referred to as its acute oral lethal dose fifty, or LD50. The oral LD50 for technical dimethoate in rats is 60 to 387 mg/kg, 60 mg/kg in mice, 400 mg/kg in dogs, 200 mg/kg in hamsters, 300 mg/kg in rabbits, 350 mg/kg in guinea pigs, and 100 mg/kg in cats (R T Meister et al., 1992). The dermal LD50 in rabbits is 1,000 mg/kg, and 353 mg/kg in rats (MSDS for Dimethoate, 1991). A dermal LD50 of greater than 2,000 mg/kg in rats has also been reported. The lethal concentration fifty, or LC50, is that concentration of a chemical in air or water that kills half of the experimental animals exposed to it for a set time period. The 4-hour LC50 for dimethoate in rats is 1.2 mg/l.

Chronic Toxicity-

There was no cholinesterase inhibition in an adult human who ingested 18 mg (about 0.26 mg/kg/day)

of dimethoate/day for 21 days. No toxic effects and no cholinesterase inhibition were observed in individuals who ingested 2.5 mg/day (about 0.04 mg/kg/day) for 4 weeks. In another study with humans, given oral doses of 5, 15, 30, 45 or 60 mg/day for 57 days, cholinesterase inhibition was observed only in the 30 mg/day or higher dosage groups (22). Repeated or prolonged exposure to organophosphates may result in the same effects as acute exposure, including the delayed symptoms. Other effects reported in workers repeatedly exposed include impaired memory and concentration, disorientation, severe depressions, irritability, confusion, headache, speech difficulties, delayed reaction times, nightmares, sleepwalking and drowsiness or insomnia. An influenza-like condition with headache, nausea, weakness, loss of appetite, and malaise has also been reported (MSDS for Dimethoate, 1991).

Reproductive Effects

When mice were given 60 ppm (9.5 to 10.5 mg/kg/day) dimethoate in their drinking water, there was decreased reproduction, pup survival, and growth rates of surviving pups. Adults in this study exhibited reduced weight gain, but their survival was not affected. In a 3- generation study with mice, 2.5 mg/kg/day did not decrease reproductive performance or pup survival (W J Hayes et al., 1990). Once in the bloodstream, dimethoate may cross the placenta.

Teratogenic Effects

Dimethoate is possibly a human teratogen. It was teratogenic in cats and rats. A dosage of 12 mg/kg/day given to pregnant cats increased the incidence of extra toes on kittens. The same dosage given to pregnant rats produced birth defects related to bone formation, runting and defects related to malfunction of the bladder. Dosages of 3 or 6 mg/kg/day were not teratogenic in cats or rats. The NOEL for both cats and rats was 2.8 mg/kg/day. There were no teratogenic effects seen in the offspring of mice given (9.5 - 10.5 mg/kg/day) dimethoate in their drinking water (W J Hayes et al., 1990).

Mutagenic Effects-

Dimethoate is possibly a mutagen (6, 14, Mutation Res. 88 (3):307- 326. 1981). Mutagenic effects (dominant lethal) were more prominent in male mice given a single high dose of dimethoate than in male mice given one-twelfth of the same dose daily for 30 days (W J Hayes et al., 1990).

Carcinogenic Effects-

Dimethoate is possibly carcinogenic (6, 14). An increase in malignant tumors was reported in rats given oral doses of 5, 15 or 30 mg/kg dimethoate for 511 to 627 days (MSDS for Dimethoate, 1991).

Organ Toxicity-

The testicles of male rats exposed to dimethoate decreased in size. These rats also developed chronic kidney problems.

Monocrotophos:

Monocrotophos is an organophosphorus (OP) insecticide, developed by Ciba-Geigy (now Novartis) and first registered in 1965. It is a hazardous chemical especially for conditions of use in developing countries. This non-specific systemic insecticide and acaricide, used to control common mites, ticks and spiders with contact and stomach action, quickly penetrates plant tissue. In common with other OPs, its toxic action is achieved by inhibiting acetylcholinesterase, an enzyme essential for normal nerve impulse transmission. It is widely used, mainly for foliar application to cotton. Monocrotophos is corrosive, and stable when stored in glass or polyethylene containers (B Kumari et al., 2003).

Fate in the environment and Wildlife:

Monocrotophos has a half-life of 14-21 days at pH9 and 25°C, with the rate decreasing at lower pH and increasing at higher temperatures. Degradation on soil exposed to natural sunlight is rapid (half-life less than 7 days) and on dark control samples is slower (half-life approximately 30 days). Monocrotophos is mobile in soil, and although it degrades rapidly it may possess potential for groundwater contamination. The major manufacturer, Novartis, joined meetings which agreed not to use monocrotophos in the region and encouraged other local distributors to stop selling the pesticide. A campaign to inform farmers was also supported by Novartis.

Food residues:

OPs do not have long persistence and are generally found at low levels in food. Monocrotophos is not used in the UK, and testing imported food in 1996 found low levels (0.03 mg/kg) in one sample of dried currants (of eight tested) imported from Greece. Testing by UK food industry sources found monocrotophos residues in dwarf beans (0.07 mg/kg). Maximum residue limits have been set in some products in the range of 0.02-1 mg/kg, and the acceptable daily take is 0.0006 mg/kg body weight. Monocrotophos and some of its metabolites have been identified in the milk, muscle, and liver of cows and in the milk of goats following ingestion of this chemical.

Pre-harvest intervals have been set in several countries and are generally in the order of 7-15 days for vegetables and potatoes, maize and citrus and 28-30 days for other crops.

Monocrotophos toxicological effects:

Acute toxicity:

Monocrotophos is classified WHO Ib, highly hazardous, and has been responsible for deaths resulting from accidental or intentional exposure. It is highly toxic orally, as well by inhalation or absorption through the skin. Early symptoms of poisoning may include excessive sweating, headache, weakness, giddiness, nausea, vomiting, hyper salivation, abdominal cramps, diarrhea, blurred vision and slurred speech. Inhalation or skin contact may increase the susceptibility to the pesticide without showing immediate symptoms (Niaz Ahmed Akhtera et al., 2003). The acute oral toxicity for rats (LD50) is 23mg/kg (males) and 18 mg/kg (females). The acute dermal toxicity for a rats is 354 mg/kg. Tests on rabbits indicate it is slightly irritating to eyes and causes reversible corneal opacity: reports on human health indicate eye contact will cause pain, bleeding, tears, pupil constriction and blurred vision. Severe poisoning will affect the central nervous system, producing inco-ordination, slurred speech, loss of reflexes, weakness, fatigue, involuntary muscle contractions, twitching, tremors of the tongue or eyelids and eventually paralysis of the body extremities and the respiratory muscles. In severe cases there may also be involuntary defecation or urination, psychosis, irregular heartbeat, unconsciousness, convulsions and coma. Ingestion of 120 mg monocrotophos can be fatal (Niaz Ahmed Akhtera et al., 2003). Like other OPs, monocrotophos is a potent cholinesterase inhibitor. The no effect level (NOEL) is 0.03 ppm in rats. It is slightly irritating to the skin and mildly irritating to the eyes.

Chronic effects

Monocrotophos has also been shown to cause delayed neuropathy (Registration Standard for the Reregistration of Pesticide Products Containing Chlorpyrifos, 2014). A study in Egypt of farmers using OPs, including monocrotophos, found that 50% of the workers showed signs of neurological effects such as superficial or deep sensory loss and decrease or lost reflexes in their ankle or ankle and knee.

Cancer

Monocrotophos is not carcinogenic in rats at 0.45 mg/kg/day, the highest dose tested. No significant carcinogenic lesions were observed when rats were exposed to monocrotophos aerosol at concentrations from 97-308 mg/m³ for one hour.

Reproductive effects:

Researchers have generated a rat reproductive (and offspring) NOEL of 2.7 ppm, evidenced by decreased fertility, pup viability and weight, partly attributed to depressed maternal lactation.

Teratogenicity (birth defects)

Rats which received doses of 2 mg/kg per day of monocrotophos produced foetuses with lower than

average length and weight and maternal toxicity in the form of reduced body weight gain in pregnancy at 1.0 mg/kg. No teratogenic effects were found at 2 mg/kg/day in rats, the highest dose tested.

Applications

They have properties of disrupting micro-organisms' cell processes and surfactants. These compounds are used as

- Active Ingredient for Conditioners
- Antistatic Agent
- Detergent Sanitizers
- Softener for textiles and paper products
- Antimicrobials
- Phase Transfer Catalyst
- Disinfection Agents And Sanitizers
- Slimicidal Agents
- Algaecide
- Emulsifying Agents
- Pigment Dispersers (Chunyan Sun et al., 2011).

III. Selection of Pesticide:

India is an agriculture-based country, about 30% of agriculture produce is lost due to pests. Hence agrochemicals like insecticides, fungicides, pesticides and herbicides have increasing demand for protection of crops in one way or the other. Thus, large numbers of pesticides are emerging out day by day. Furthermore, the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO) has estimated that more than 400,000 tonnes of obsolete pesticides are stocked worldwide. The disposal of EDCs such as pesticides, fungicides and insecticides can cause serious environmental problems due to the chemical toxicity of the active ingredients in the formulations and sometimes, of their decomposition products. In the United States, OPs represent about half of the total insecticides used, with annual applications over 75 million pounds (B Kumari et al., 2003). Nowadays organochlorine (OC) pesticides are not used primarily due to their persistence in the environment. At this time, the use of OPs glided due to their availability and quick degradation in the environment. OPs have been widely manufactured and used in the world. And they replaced the chlorinated pesticides. A survey of the study area Punjab was carried out to assess the extent of widely used pesticides before sample collection and analysis. In the survey, 240 farmers from four districts were interviewed to through a well-structured questionnaire to judge the extent of pesticide use, practices related to the application of the pesticides and equipments and safety measures. Results of the survey showed that many OPs pesticides were used but four insecticides (Triazophos, Profenofos Chlorpyrifos and Malathion) were widely used in the area on the vegetable crops (Niaz Ahmed Akhtera et al., 2003).

Table 1. Pesticides according to their class and level of toxicity

Pesticide	Class	Level of Toxicity
Chlorpyrifos	II	Moderately Toxic
Malathion	II	Moderately Toxic
Dimethoate	II	Moderately Toxic

Table 2. Pesticide consumption in India grams /hectare

STATE	1999-2001
Andhra Pradesh	302
Bihar	82
Gujarat	331
Haryana	827
Karnataka	201
Madhya Pradesh	61
Maharashtra	168
Punjab	889
Tamilnadu	261
Uttar Pradesh	285
West Bengal	372

Pesticide residues on crops are monitored through the use of Maximum Residue Limits (MRL), which are based on the analysis of the quantity of a given chemical remaining on food product samples. The MRL is usually determined by repeated of field trials, where the crop has been treated according to good agricultural practice and an appropriate pre harvest interval or withholding period has elapsed. For many pesticides this is set at the Limit of Determination (LOD) – since only major pesticides have been evaluated and understanding of Acceptable daily intake (ADI) is incomplete (i.e. producers or public bodies have not submitted MRL data – often because these were not required in the past). LOD can be considered a measure of presence/absence, but certain residues may not be quantifiable at very low levels. For this reason the limit of quantification (LOQ) is often used instead of the LOD. As a rule of thumb the LOQ is approximately two times the LOD. For substances that are not included in any of the annexes in EU regulations, a default MRL of 0.01 mg/kg normally applies.

Safety of MRLs:

An interesting exercise done by Centre for Science and Environment on the non-compatibility between ADI and MRLs in India brings forth the fact that even if MRLs are prescribed are followed in reality, they would be far beyond the ADI levels fixed for each pesticide. Therefore, the question to be asked is "How Safe Are MRLs? MRLs can be considered safe only if the cumulative daily intake of

pesticides remains within the ADI [which is supposed to be worked out based on chronic toxicity]. Such cumulative daily intake depends on the individual [child or adult], the socio-cultural context of dietary intake and on the Theoretical Maximum Daily Intake [TMDI] of pesticides worked out on this basis. CSE did an exercise of calculating the actual TMDI against the ADIs and MRLs of around eight pesticides for the average Indian diet. In the case of Monocrotophos, for example, they first put down the Indian MRL [in mg/kg body weight] for various food commodities like wheat, rice, pulses, vegetables, vegetable oils, milk etc. As per the diets of an average Indian, the total pesticide intake of Monocrotophos for an average adult, for an average Indian diet works out to be 0.1510 mg/day. The prescribed Average Daily Intake of Monocrotophos is 0.0360, based on chronic toxicity potential. Therefore, the total pesticide intake theoretically works out to be 419% more than the ADI. There are other detailed total diet studies which have also reflected similar findings. This raises basic points about the way MRLs are fixed, almost cut away from the ADIs being prescribed through health impact studies. This questions the very validity of considering MRLs as an indication of how safe our food is and the fact that almost all pesticide surveillance rests on such parameters (K Kuruganti et al., 2007).

Table 3. Indicates the extent of pesticide residues in various agricultural commodities monitored under all India Network Project on pesticide residues on Vegetables, [ICAR].

Year	No. of Samples Analyzed	Samples above MRL (%)
1999	277	10 (3.36%)
2000	712	81 (11%)
2001	796	93 (11.7%)
2002	592	54 (9%)
2003	666	35 (5.3%)
Total 1999-2003	3043	273 (8.97%)

Selection of sample (Vegetable- Brinjal):

Brinjal, *Solanum melongena* L. (scientific name) is a very common and favorite vegetable among the Indians. It is an important vegetable grown in all the seasons. Due to its nutritive value, consisting of minerals like iron, phosphorous, calcium and vitamins like A, B and C, unripe fruits are used primarily as vegetable in the country. It is also used as a raw material in pickle making and as an excellent remedy for those suffering from liver complaints. It is estimated that there are more than hundred varieties of brinjal in our country. Brinjal is cultivated in almost every part of our country since last 4,000 years (The North-east India is also known for brinjal cultivation. It has been observed that like other parts of our country, the brinjal cultivated also suffers from

several diseases and pests. The most common pests are the Stem and Fruit Borer Worms (SFBW) along with fungal and viral diseases. To get good crop yield, the farmers have to spray a large quantity of pesticides and fungicides. Fruit and shoot borer (FSB) is the most devastating insect-pest of brinjal, which causes 60-70% yield loss, besides deteriorating product quality. Farmers rely mainly on the application of chemical pesticides to control FSB. The chemical control involves excessive and indiscriminate use of pesticides, causing multiple side-effects that include exposure of farm labourers and consumers to pesticide residues, increased cost of cultivation, environmental pollution, destruction of natural enemies of pests, and resurgence of pest population, etc. (Performance of Multi-location Research Trials of Bt Brinjal Hybrids, 2007). Although insecticidal control is one of the common means against the fruit borer, many of the insecticides applied are not effective in the satisfactory control of this pest. Brinjal being a vegetable crop, use of chemical insecticides will leave considerable toxic residues on the fruits. Beside this, sole dependence on insecticides for the control of this pest has led to insecticidal resistance by the pest. Hence, use of organic amendments, plant products and microbial origin insecticides can be the novel approaches to manage the pest

Production Profile of Brinjal:

More than 2000 varieties of brinjal are grown in India. Amongst different states, West Bengal comes at the top with 28% share in national brinjal production, followed by Orissa (21%), Bihar (12%) and Gujarat (10%) during triennium ending (TE) 2009. On the yield front, both Bihar and Karnataka produced about 21 t/ha, while West Bengal, Gujarat, Maharashtra, and Andhra Pradesh were at par with country's average yield of 17t/ha. A significant progress has been made in the production of brinjal during the past two decades (Figure 1). Between 1991 and 2009, area under brinjal cultivation increased by 52.6% (from 3.8 lakh ha to 5.8 lakh ha), production increased by 94% (from 50.6 lakh tonnes to 98.1 lakh tonnes), and yield rose by 26.8% (from 13.4 t/ha to 17.0 t/ha). These data show that increase in brinjal production has largely been driven by increase in its area, though yield-increase also contributed to it. Given the serious constraint on area expansion, productivity increase will be the main source of output growth in future (Krishna V. V. et al., 2008). The pesticide application to this crop was more than the other crops. The minimum range of pesticide-use intensity was 3-4 kg of a.i/ha and 31.43 per cent of the farms were within this range. The inter-farm variation in pesticide-use intensity ranged from 3.10 kg of a.i/ha to 8.65 kg of a.i/ha with average of 4.64 kg of a.i/ha. Same number of farmers was observed in all the pesticide-use intensity ranges, except in the case of more than 6 kg

of a.i/ha, in which only 5.71 per cent farmers were observed (N P Agnihotri., 2000).

Table 4. Indicates the extent of pesticides residues in several agricultural commodities monitored under all India Network Project on Pesticide residues on Fruits, [ICAR].

YEAR	NO. Of Samples Analyzed	Samples above MRL (%)
1999	122	8(6%)
2000	378	8(6%)
2001	378	0(0%)
2002	359	3(0.8%)
2003	317	1(0.3%)
Total 1999-2003	1554	15 (0.97%)

Selection of Sample (Fruit- Grapes):

The Environmental Working Group (EWG), a non-profit advocacy agency has released their list of the most contaminated fruits and vegetables and apples have been ranked as the most contaminated - fifth year in a row. The Dirty Dozen list includes the top 12 fruits and veggies with the highest amount of pesticide residues. The agency hopes to enlighten people so they study the list, stay away from this produce and go for the organic options instead, at least for these 12 items. According to a statement, the EWG's Shopper's Guide to Pesticides in Produce ranked pesticide contamination on 48 popular fruits and vegetables based on an analysis of more than 34,000 samples taken by the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) and federal Food and Drug Administration. It was found that pesticides persisted on fruits and vegetables even when they were washed or peeled. This can't be good, especially when pesticides have been linked to a range of health problems, including cancer, developmental problems and lower IQ in children. A single grape sample contained 15 pesticides (most of them OPs) due to which the grapes are banned in European countries (Aman Zalawadia et al., 2015).

Conclusion

The benefits of pesticides include increased food production, increased profits for farmers and the prevention of diseases. Although pests consume or harm a large portion of agricultural crops, without the use of pesticides, it is likely that they would consume a higher percentage. Due to the use of pesticides, it is possible to produce larger quantities of food. By producing more crops, farmers are also able to increase. Pesticides also increase farm profits by helping the farmer save money on labor costs. Using pesticides reduces the amount of time required to manually remove weeds and pests from fields. In addition to saving crops and livestock, pesticides have also had direct benefits to human health. The

use of pesticides has prevented the deaths of around seven million people by killing pests that carry or transmit diseases. Malaria, which is transmitted by infected mosquitoes, is one of the most commonly known and deadly diseases that has decreased in prevalence due to the use of pesticides. Other diseases that were minimized due to the use of pesticides include the bubonic plague, which is carried by rat fleas, and typhus, which is transmitted by both fleas and body lice. Pesticides are mobile in the environment and often move through water, air and soil, with mobility they come in contact with other organism and can cause harm, disturbs ecosystem kill non- pests organisms, causes poisonings, and development of cancer. Another major problem associated with pesticide use is bioaccumulation means synthetic pesticides enter the body of an organism, they are permanently stored in the body tissue and biological magnification means pesticides, increase in concentration with each level of the food chain synthetic pesticides enter the body of an organism; they are permanently stored in the body tissue. Therefore it is highly required to eliminate pesticides from fruits and vegetables.

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Conflict of Interests:

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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